

Effect of Post Tender Negotiations on Performance of Commercial State Corporations in Kenya

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Abstract

The main aim of the study was to establish the effect of post-tender negotiations on performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. The study was 27 commercial state corporations in Government in Nairobi County. The study adopted simple random technique to select a sample size of 84 respondents. The data was collected by use of a questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was tested through use of Crobach Alpha value. Data were analyzed using descriptive (Frequencies, percentage informed by dynamic capability theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population on focus comprised of 108 employees from, mean and standard deviations) and inferential statistics such as Pearson's correlations and multiple regression). From the findings supplier capability and payment terms affected the performance in commercial State Corporation in Kenya. Based on the study findings, the study concluded that supplier capabilities and payment terms affected performance of commercial State Corporation in Kenya. The study has confirmed that post tender negotiations are very significant in enhancing the performance of commercial state owned enterprises in Kenya. The study recommends that there is need to enhance supplier financial capability, supplier competence through training. The study recommends that there is need to improve on the organizations' negotiation on the advance payments. The terms of payment should be clearly explained to all parties in the phase and periodic payments.

Keywords: Post Tender Negotiations, Performance, Commercial State Corporations Supplier Capabilities, Payment Terms

Introduction

Organizations today are constantly in search of ways to achieve better business performance and sustain competitive advantages through the effective deployment of resources and business processes (Faizal, 2015). To improve business performance, organizations require an efficient leadership. Most organizations view their performance in terms of "effectiveness" in achieving their mission, vision, purpose or goals. Most public organizations for example commercial banks would tend to link the larger notion of firm performance to the results of their service delivery to the public (Abdullateef, Mokhtar & Yusoff, 2013). At the same time, a majority of organizations also see their performance in terms of their "efficiency" in deploying resources. This relates to the optimal use of resources to obtain the results desired (Amin, 2012). Finally, in order for an organization to remain viable over time, it must be both "financially viable" and "relevant" to its stakeholders and their changing needs.

In today's world, supply chain performance is a key strategic factor for increasing organizational effectiveness and for better realization of organizational goals such as enhanced competitiveness, better customer care and increased profitability (Bosman, 2016). The globalization of markets and outsourcing has made many manufacturing companies logistics capabilities to manage their operations. Most of these companies realize that, in order to evolve an efficient and effective supply chain, SCM needs to be assessed for its performance (Van & Beulens, 2012). Tendering and post tender negotiation are core components of purchasing and supply management and, as such, all purchasing and supply management professionals should be competent in their implementation.

Post-Tender Negotiation (PTN) procedure is part of the tendering process in the procurement of goods and services. The procedure could be triggered if the initial tendering activity does not result in the selection of a supplier. This could be due to a lack of clear Value for Money (VfM) bidder. The PTN procedure is sparingly applied in the public sector procurement and the reasons adduced for this are based on ethical considerations (Shengjie & Jiangang, 2015)

According to Rolim 2016) Post Tender Negotiation (PTN) used in this Guidance is: "Negotiation after receipt of formal bids or tenders and before the letting of contract(s) with those companies submitting tender(s) offering the best value for money with a view to obtaining an improvement in content in circumstances which do not put the other tenderers at a disadvantage, distort competition or affect adversely trust in the competitive tendering process." During the competitive tendering process, PTN may be used to secure value for money, provided that the adverse effects on competition referred to in the definition above are avoided. PTN is part of the competitive tendering process, bearing in mind that public purchasing policy is to use competition wherever possible and that the Kenyan international obligations normally require such competition for purchases above certain thresholds. Hence, PTN is the exploration by the parties of the means by which the purchaser can achieve a better deal on a mutually acceptable basis. However, there are limited studies in the area of PTN. Many researchers (Rolim, 2016; Bangs, Murrell & Constance-Huggins, 2014) have dwelled mostly on tendering thus, contributing to a gap in the literature of PTN. Thus, while the bidding/tendering process has received some attention, the PTN as a process within the tendering process have not been adequately discussed, hence the need for research to be done in this area

Earlier studies have pointed out that tender negotiations practices are a critical factor in steering the company's survival and growth (Gupta & Sharma, 2014), however, the decline of performance in most corporations around the globe have been attributed to the supply chain management practices (Hussainey & Al-Najjar, 2012; Ntim *et al.*, 2012a; Ademola *et al.*, 2016). In the recent past, majority of commercial State Corporation have been experiencing weakening financial performance, and forecasts too have indicated a similar trend in the future (Ogwoka *et al.*, 2017). The procurement function usually takes large amounts of organization's revenue (Amin, 2012). In the year 2013/14, the GOK expected to spend about 70% of the 1.6 Trillion shillings budget on procurement of goods and services.

The procurement function is becoming an expensive undertaking for many organizations and if not properly done it can lead to significant regret. The tendering negotiation process of any organization is costly. Numerous costs are incurred during the tendering process. Administrative costs such as cost of preparing tender documents, inviting of tenders, opening of tenders, costs for evaluation of tenders and verifying the documents should be reduced. This will aid in improving the procurement performance (Khain, 2012). If tendering is not well managed a company will incur numerous costs. Tendering has to be performed correctly in order to maximize effectiveness and minimize costs. The duration was taken in tendering significantly influences the effectiveness of tendering (Ayoti, 2013). Mm

There is a general consensus among previous researchers globally, that indeed, there exists a link between post-tender negotiations and financial performance (Akinkoye & Olasanmi, 2014; Mwangi *et al.*, 2014). However, the results are inconclusive and the overall effect of post-tender negotiations on performance of commercial State Corporations still remains unclear (Black, 2006) especially in the emerging economies, not excluding Kenya where the focus of the previous studies has been to test the relation of specific post-tender negotiations (Nyamongo & Temesgen, 2013; Manini & Abdillahi, 2015) and not on the overall effect of post-tender negotiations to performance. Therefore, this study is motivated by all these questionable events as well as the continuous weakening in performance of commercial State Corporations to establish the effect of corporate governance practices on performance of commercial State Corporation in Kenya. Previous research explained the PTN procedure without discussing how the procedure can significantly influence VfM purchases and the factors that

could ensure the application of the procedure's success. Thus, there is the need for research to be carried out to establish the effects of the PTN procedure and also identify the factors that would lead to the success of its application, particularly in the public sector procurements in Kenya.

Theoretical Literature Review

This study was informed by Dynamic Capabilities Theory. Dynamic capabilities were proposed by Helfat and Peteraf (2015), which is defined "the capacity of an organization to create purposefully, extend, or modify its resource base" and as such to reach a higher economic value than its competitors. In addition, dynamic capabilities are regarded as a transformer for converting resources into improved performance. Chien and Tsai (2012) argue that dynamic capabilities are 'the foundation of enterprise-level competitive advantage in regimes of rapid (technological) change.' He further argues that dynamic capabilities are component capabilities that are 'necessary to sustain superior enterprise performance' in a highly dynamic environment. Chowdhury and Quaddus (2017) refined this definition of dynamic capabilities to the ability to sense and then seize new opportunities, and to reconfigure and protect knowledge assets, competencies, and complementary assets with the aim of achieving a sustained competitive advantage. There is no broad consensus on an operational definition of dynamic capabilities and this makes it difficult to identify a generally accepted scale for measuring dynamic capabilities.

More specifically, Zollo and Winter (2012) define dynamic capabilities as learned and stable patterns of collective activity through which the organization systemically generates and modifies operating routines in pursuit of improved effectiveness. Teece (2007) later defines it as the ability to sense and then seize new opportunities and to reconfigure these to achieve strategy implementation. Chien and Tsai (2012) expand this definition to the inimitable capacity firms have to shape, re-shape, configure and reconfigure the firm's asset base so as to respond to changing technologies and markets. With dynamic capabilities, sustained strategy implementation comes from the firm's ability to leverage and reconfigure its existing competencies and assets in ways that are valuable to the customer but difficult for other competitors to imitate. Dynamic capabilities help firm's sense opportunities and then seize them by successfully reallocating resources, often by adjusting existing competencies or developing new ones (Manso & Nikas, 2015). Dynamic capabilities can usefully be thought of as belonging to three clusters of activities and adjustments: identification and assessment of an opportunity (sensing); mobilization of resources to address an opportunity and to capture value from doing so (seizing); and continued renewal of core competencies (transforming) (Lee & Wu, 2014).). One key implication of the dynamic capabilities concept is that firms are not only competing on their ability to exploit their existing resources and organizational capabilities, firms are also competing on their ability to explore, renew and develop their organizational capabilities. Thus, dynamic capabilities allow a firm to sense opportunities and then to seize them by successfully allocation resources by adjusting existing competencies or developing new ones. This is especially true for ITC companies competing in global changing markets

Dynamic capabilities refer to the firm's processes that use resources to match and even create market change; thus, the organizational and strategic routines by which firms achieve new resource configuration as markets emerge, collide, split, evolve, and die (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2013). Dynamic capabilities are valuable in virtually all levels of environmental turbulence, implying that managers must continuously try to identify new opportunities and make decisions to reconfigure their existing operational capabilities, irrespective of the level of environmental turbulence (Pavlou & Sawy, 2011). Therefore, this theory was applied in the study to discuss supplier capability on the performance of commercial State Corporation.

Literature review

Supplier Capability

Capability, in general, is a new concept, very applied in the literature but with little consensus about what it really means. It is generally accepted that every firm has a set of capabilities; those let the firm perform a unique entity. Supplier financial capabilities are firm-specific sets of funds, within the operations management system, that are regularly used in solving problem procurement process (Flynn *et al.* 2010). In terms of supply chain activities, financial capability is linked to the supplier's ability in the aspects of handling correct orders and delivery without any challenge (Nurwin, 2018).

Supplier competence capabilities are generated by sets of skills and resources to contribute to value-added tasks (Wilding *et al.*, 2012). Fundamentally, capability and assets have a mutual connection with each other. However, capability is slightly different from asset, in terms of its inability to provide monetary value, tangible plants and equipment to a firm, and also it cannot be traded and imitated (Manso & Nikos, 2015). Capability can also be referred as "the exploitation of specific practices to attain performance gains" (Amin, 2012). It can be concluded that capability and practice are different in several aspects because various plants are feasible to invest equally in practice, but they do not have the same degree of capability to achieve a good manufacturing performance outcome (Chien & Tsai, 2012).

Other studies on the subject were held in a broader perspective. Amin (201) proposed seven relevant skills in the context of operations, identifying categories as improvement, innovation, integration, accuracy, control, agility and responsiveness. Flynn *et al.* (2010), taking the research of Swink and Hegarty (2018) as a basis, sought to clarify the limits of capability. Based on the extensive theoretical review, the authors defined six key operational capabilities, which served as the basis for the preparation of the present study

Studies have acknowledged the importance of logistics capabilities in imparting the firm with a competitive advantage (Gligor & Holcomb, 2012). Logistics capabilities are those specialized skills, attributes and knowledge within a firm that helps a firm to manage its logistics activities (for e.g. transportation and distribution of raw materials and finished goods) efficiently and effectively (Gligor & Holcomb, 2012). Although the terms, logistics and supply chain have been used interchangeably, the current study distinguished between the two and posited logistics as an integral part of supply chain management. Logistics capabilities do influence the way a firm operates in the market. Lynch et al. (2010) investigated the effect of logistics capabilities and strategy on firm performance. Capabilities are the skills and knowledge that enable firms to make use of their assets. Logistics capabilities are capabilities that essentially support the logistics functions of the firms to be executed properly. The study conceptualized strategy as either cost leadership or differentiation. The study proposed that corporate strategy is most effective when pursued with resources/capabilities that -fit.

SCM and operational capability continue to play critical roles in influencing a firm's ability to compete in the market. Studies are increasingly looking across the supply chain, beyond their encompassing concept, to establish the link between operations and SCM (Robb et al., 2008; Chen and Kim, 2007; Zhang and Dhaliwal, 2009; Oliva and Watson, 2011), with the aim of creating a seamless flow of goods/services and information from suppliers and operations to the customers. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the linkages between SCI and operational capability have not yet been addressed explicitly and modeled collectively. Indeed, previous studies have found there is a link between SCM practices and firm performance (Tan, 2002; Min and Mentzer, 2004; Li et al., 2005; Chow et al., 2008; Chong et al., 2011; Cook et al., 2011).

Cho et al. (2008) empirically examined the relationship between a firm's logistics capability, logistics outsourcing and its performance in an e-commerce market environment. The study argued that e-commerce firms have a higher likelihood of creating a sustainable competitive advantage and improving performance if they have strong logistics capability. Studies have also explored the direct contribution of logistics capabilities

to competitive advantage. Sandberg and Abrahamsson (2011) explored the link between (operational and dynamic) logistics capabilities and sustainable competitive advantage. The study used two Swedish retail companies to investigate the proposed links. The study used resource based view as the theoretical backdrop for the aforesaid study. The study argued that the success of these two Swedish companies was based on logistics: operational and dynamic capabilities.

Payment Terms

Willingness to issue payment terms extension as well as reduce costs among trading partners seriously affects the performance of any adopted supply chain financing mechanisms adopted by firms. Frequent changing of firm suppliers is likely to disrupt optimal SCF performance as new suppliers may be receptive to adopting such a financing system as advocated for by the firm. Supplier replacements essentially lead to periods of time needed to build up mutual relationships between suppliers and buyers hence impeding the success of SCF performance (Sezen, 2008).

According to Manso and Nikos (2015), a regular disbursement of interim payment is a critical point for a contractor to keep them alive. Whether it's a late payment or not being paid in the amounts certified, it all literally means big problems to the contractors as cash flow will be effected. Some small construction companies would close business due to late payments. The schemes for reimbursing the contractor for works done under a typical construction contract as varied as the types of such contracts encountered in practice.

Lip (2013) concluded that during the years, with the diminished volume of construction work, contractors are reeling under relentless pressure to tender with little or non-existent margins or as most aptly called 'suicide' bids just to sustain the flow of work orders. Payment to contractors or lack of it is a common cause of disputes in the construction industry. Timeliness of payments affects many contractors, for whom receiving delayed payments from their employers is a cause of friction between the two parties.

Meng (2015) in his works stated that all problems in construction begin when payment is not received at the exact amount or date. Disagreements then lead to arguments as relationships sour, and the stage becomes a setting for conflict, blame, finger-pointing, buck-passing and lawyers. Projects exceed initial time and cost estimates and experience extensive delays. But contractors are the ones who suffer the most when things like this occur. This is the case especially when Design and Built construction contracts are practised more and more nowadays. Delayed payments never bring justice to contractors. Sub-contractors are very much the same, if not worse condition, because of late payment (Artidi & Chotibongs, 2015). Its effects sometimes are so harsh that some companies had to close due to payment issues. One of the biggest consequences would be the interest. Interest is a fact of life in the world of business, and the construction industry of Malaysia is no exception.

Nurwin (2015) studied the risks affecting construction delays and cost overruns in building projects in Surabaya and Denpasar, Indonesia. They identified the most critical factors as high inflation/increased material price, design change by the client, defective design; weather conditions; delayed payment on contracts and defective construction work. Hoffmann *et al.* (2014) delays can occur in any and all activities, and these delays can concurrently or simultaneously cause delays in the project completion. In other words, a project delay is the accumulated effect of the delays in individual activities. Delays can give rise to disruption of work and loss of productivity, late completion of project, increased time-related costs and third-party claims and abandonment or termination of contract. Methods of minimizing construction delays can be established when causes of delays are identified. Knowing the cause of any particular delay in a construction project would help to avoid the same.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a descriptive survey approach focusing on post tender negotiations on the performance of commercial state corporations in Nairobi. The population on focus in this study comprised of 108 officers in departments involved in the procurement related matters in the identified commercial state corporations in Kenya. The sampling frame to be used as the human resource register of the 27 commercial state corporations in Government. The study adopted simple random technique to select 108 respondents. Data collected mainly through questionnaires. The questionnaires used for the study comprised of close-ended questions. The questionnaire was structured with likert scale to quantify the responses. The quantitative data obtained was analysed using both descriptive (means, standard deviations, frequencies and illustrations) and inferential statistics (ANOVA and t test were used for testing significant differences, Pearson correlation for determining relationships and multiple regression analysis for assessing the extent of the effect of independent variables on dependent variable. This. The regression model is represented below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Where

Y =Performance of commercial state firms

β_0 =Constant

X_1 =Supplier capability

X_2 =Payment terms

Results

This section presents and discusses the results of this study based on the formulated objectives and research questions as presented in chapter one. The researcher distributed 84 questionnaires to the respondents. 79 questionnaires out of the 84 were returned, which gives a response rate of approximately 94.04%. This response rate is above average. Even though the percentage rate of response was above average, the number of distributed questionnaires may have implications on the validity of the statistical analysis. The response rate was considered adequate given that Yin (2017) argued that a response of more than 75% would give rise to best analysis.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Results

The overall mean response for supplier capabilities was 3.79 (SD = 0.384), indicating overall agreement by majority of the employees regarding aspects of supplier capabilities with the exception of sharing of risk between the commercial state corporations and the suppliers. Assessment of the standard deviations shows that all of them are within the +/-1.96 range which is the approximate value of the 95 percentile point of the normal distribution. The overall mean was 3.56 (SD = 0.780) regarding payment terms. All the standard deviations are within the +/-1.96 range for a normal distribution. the mean response regarding performance was 4.02 (SD = 0.780), indicating considerable level of performance in the commercial State Corporation in Kenya. The findings in table 4.10 show that supplier capabilities have a positive and significant relationship with performance, $\rho = 0.712$, $p < 0.05$. This means that there is a probability of 0.712 that performance would increase given an increase in supplier capabilities. Furthermore, the findings show that payment terms have a positive and significant relationship with performance, $\rho = 0.621$, $p < 0.05$ meaning that there is a 0.621 probability that performance will increase with increase in payment terms between the suppliers and the commercial state corporation in Kenya

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Results

	Mean	Std	Performance	Supplier Capabilities	Payment Terms
Performance	4.020	0.780	1		
Supplier Capabilities	3.790	0.384	.712**	1	
Payment Terms	3.560	0.780	.621**	.609**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Regression Model

The regression analysis, in this case, is used to assess the effect of the independent factors on the dependent factor (performance) and answer the underlying research objectives. According to the findings in 2. Table, coefficient of determination (R squared) for the relationship between the two independent variables (payment terms and supplier capabilities) and performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya was 0.682. This implies that the two, payment terms and supplier capabilities can explain 68.20% of the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. This shows that other factors not included in this study explain 31.80% of the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. Thus, the post-tender negotiations factors (payment terms and supplier capabilities) need to be considered to enhance performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. The findings, as shown in Table 2, show that the F-calculated (39.234) was greater than the F-critical (4, 74) which was 13.543 and the p-value (0.000) was less than the significance level (0.05). This shows that the linear regression model is a good fit for the data and chances are zero that the result of regression model are due to random events instead of a true relationship hence can be used to assess the effect of the four independent variables (payment terms and supplier capabilities) on the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya.

The findings in table 2 show that supplier capabilities have a significant effect on performance, $\beta_1 = 0.205$, $p < 0.05$. However, despite these findings, successful relationships in service settings are attributed to supplier capabilities, cost savings and technology sharing (echtelt, 2018). Furthermore, Amin (2013) indicated that supplier partnership enables both parties to improve decision making process, enhance knowledge sharing, advance communication, and improve the overall performance of both parties. Supplier capabilities result in reduced costs, improved communication, risk-sharing, and improved problem solving (Nurwin, 2018).

The second objective of this study was to find out if payment terms with suppliers affect performance at commercial State Corporation in Kenya. The study aimed to answer the research question that: does payment terms with suppliers affect performance at commercial State Corporation in Kenya? The findings in Table 2 show that payment terms have a positive and significant effect on performance, $\beta_2 = 0.189$, $p < 0.05$. This means that with each unit increase in payment terms, performance increases by 0.191 units. In line with these findings, trust between the buying firm and its suppliers would improve cooperation, enhance satisfaction, reduce conflicts, facilitate information exchange, and lead to long-term relationships (Apopa, 2018). In addition, trust-building should not be the concern of the buying firm only. Lou and Alshawi (2009) concluded that trust is also essential and advantageous to the supplier firm, which has to make efforts to establish, extend, and retain the buying firm trust, especially when such trust can lead to more benefits for the supplier.

Table 2 **Regression results**

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	0.639	0.263		2.430	0.018
Supplier Capability	0.205	0.086	0.226	2.384	0.003
Payment terms	0.189	0.095	0.147	1.989	0.013
Model statistics					
R	0.826				
R Square	0.682				
Adjusted R Square	0.664				
model fitness statistics					
F	39.524				
Sig.	0.000				

Conclusion

As per the findings of the study it can be concluded that all the independent variables (supplier capabilities and payment terms) in the study influences the performance of commercial state corporations (dependent variable). The relationship was confirmed through correlation and regression analysis, which revealed that there was a positive significant linear relationship between supplier capabilities and payment terms. Therefore, the study concluded that supplier capabilities, payment terms influence performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya.

The study revealed positive correlations between supplier capability (financial capability, payment terms and bid clarification) and performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. It was determined that a unit increase in supplier capability resulted in an increase in performance of commercial state corporations. Subsequently, the study concludes that appropriate supplier capability in the organizations is likely to register improved performance of commercial state corporations.

In addition to the foregoing study revealed positive correlations between payment terms (advance payments, phase payments and periodic payments) and performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. It was determined that a unit increase in payment terms resulted in an increase in performance of commercial state corporations. Subsequently, the study concludes that appropriate payment terms in the organizations are likely to enhance performance of commercial state corporations.

Recommendation

The study established that supplier capabilities affected performance at commercial State Corporation in Kenya. The study recommends that there is a need to enhance supplier financial capability, supplier competence through training so that they can successfully utilize time-based logistics solutions like continuous replenishment, quick response and Just-in-Time with suppliers. The organizations' should have competent suppliers and capture the experience and expertise of supplier. The suppliers should be responsive to improve performance of the commercial state corporations.

The study established that payment terms affected the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. The study recommends that there is need to improve on the organizations' negotiation on the advance payments. The terms of payment should be clearly explained to all parties in the phase and periodic payments. The study recommends that there is need to improve on corporate prices per unit to significantly improve the delivery of goods and services in time in the state corporations in Kenya.

This research study was conducted in commercial state corporations in Kenya and hence the findings cannot be generalized to other public institutions. This study, therefore, suggests further studies on the effect of post-tender negotiations on the performance of non-commercial state corporations in Kenya. The study also found that post tender negotiations explained 68.20% of the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya. The study, therefore, suggests further studies on the other factors affecting the performance of commercial state corporations in Kenya.

REFERENCES

- i. Abdullateef, A. O., Mokhtar, S. S. M., &Yusoff, R. Z. (2013). *Linkages between CRM technologies, knowledge applications and first call resolution in inbound call centres. International Journal of Electronic Customer Relationship Management*, 7(1), 68-86.
- ii. Ademola, G. O., Samuel O. J. &Ifedolapo, O. (2016). *The Roles of Record Keeping In the Survival and Growth of Small Scale Enterprises in Ijumu Local Government Area of Kogi State. Global Journal of Management and Business Research*,12(13), 54-66
- iii. Akinkoye, E.Y. & Olasanmi, O.O. (2014). *Corporate governance practice and level of compliance among firms in Nigeria: Industry analysis. Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 9(1).
- iv. Amin, K. A. (2012). *Electronic procurement and organizational performance among commercial state corporations. Unpublished MBA Project, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya.*
- v. Apopa, Vincensia Anyango 2018. *Influence of Supply Chain Management Practices on Performance of Government Ministries in Kenya. School Of Business, School Of Entrepreneurship, Procurement And Management, School Of Communication And Development Studies, College of Human Resource Development (COHRED).(JKUAT)*
- vi. Bangs, R., Murrell, A., & Constance-Huggins, M. (2014). *Minority bidding for local government contracts: The complexity of availability. Social Work in Public Health*, 23(2)247-262
- vii. Black, B S., Love, I & Rachinsky, A 2006: "Corporate Governance and Firms' Market Values: Time Series Evidence from Russia". *Emerging Markets Review*, 7(2), 361-379,.
- viii. Bosman, Rick. & Scholten, Daniel (2016). *The geopolitics of renewables; exploring the political implications of renewable energy systems .Technological Forecasting and Social Change. 103. 273-283*
- ix. Chien, S. Y., & Tsai, C. H. (2012). *Dynamic capability, knowledge, learning, and firm performance. Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 25(3), 434-444.
- x. Cho, H. 2000. *Public opinion as personal cultivation. A normative notion and a source of social control in traditional china. An international Journal of public Opinion Research* 12, 299-323
- xi. Faizal M, Banwet D, Shankar R (2015) *Supply chain risk mitigation: modeling the enablers. Bus Process Manage J* 12(4):535–552
- xii. Hussainey, K., & Al-Najjar, B. (2012). *Understanding the determinants of RiskMetrics/ISS Ratings of the quality of UK companies' corporate governance practice. Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 29(4), 366-377
- xiii. Lou, E. C. W., & Alshawi, M. (2009). *Critical success factors for e-tendering implementation in construction collaborative environments: people and process issues. Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, 14, 98-109.
- xiv. Manini, M. & Abdillahi, U. (2015). *Corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Journal of Business and Management*, 17(3), 25-40
- xv. Manso, P. F., & Nikas, A. (2015). *Examining the Effects of Post Tender Negotiation in UK's Public Sector Procurements: An Empirical Study. Procedia Computer Science*, 64, 457-465.
- xvi. Mwangi, M., Birundu, E.M. (2014). *The effect of capital structure on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Thika-sub-county, Kenya. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 5(1),151-156

- xvii. Nurwin, F. R. (2018). *Effect of Regulated Electronic Tendering Practices on the Implementation of Preference Regulations in Kenyan State Corporations*. *Journal of Supply Chain Management Systems*, 7(1), 25.
- xviii. Nyamongo, E. & Temesgen, K. (2013). *The effect of governance on performance of commercial banks in Kenya: A panel study, corporate governance*. *The International Journal of Business in Society*, 13(3), 236-248
- xix. Rolim, F., Brasileiro, A. & Santos, E. (2016) 'Competition in Brazilian bus and coach services - The results of recent competitive tendering processes', *Research In Transportation Economics*, 29 (1), 45-51
- xx. Shengjie, Y. & Jiangang, Y. (2015) 'A learning method to evaluate a generation company's bidding strategy in the electricity market', *Turkish Journal Of Electrical Engineering & Computer Sciences*, 22 (1), 34-42
- xxi. Wilding, R., Wagner, B., Gimenez, C., & Tachizawa, E. M. (2012). *Extending sustainability to suppliers: a systematic literature review*. *Supply Chain Management: an international journal*.